

ROBIN: AN ALGORITHMIC COMPOSER FOR INTERACTIVE SCENARIOS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to present Robin, an algorithmic composer specifically designed for interactive situations. Users can interact in real time with the algorithmic composition by means of control strategies based on emotions. This study aims at providing a system for automatic music generation to be applied to interactive systems for music creation targeted at non-musicians. Robin adopts a rule-based approach to compose original tonal music in classical piano style. The first practical application of Robin is The Music Room, an interactive installation which enables people to compose tonal music in pairs by communicating emotion expressed by moving throughout a room.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1978 Bischoff et al. stated the relevance of music: “*to bring into play the full bandwidth of communication there seems to be no substitute [...] than the playing of music live*” [1]. However, due to complexity which is intrinsic to playing, most people can only experience melodies created by somebody else. Research in Computer Music has been trying to simplify music creation, for the purpose of making this creative art accessible to an untrained audience [2,3]. Novel technologies, such as ubiquitous computers, touchscreen devices, visual tracking systems and physiological sensors, have been used to build new devices to complement or replace traditional instruments [4,5]. This technological advancement aroused a new set of issues, opening a challenging task to interaction designers and algorithm developers.

From an interaction design perspective, the challenge is to find new metaphors, as to detach the process of music composition from theoretical knowledge and practical skills that are the result of a formal musical education. There is a need for new interaction paradigms leveraging the communication forms, with the specific requirements of being available to everybody, intuitive and naturally connected with music. Emotion is probably the language that best meets the requirements mentioned above. In every culture, music is one of the arts that most effectively stir emotions [6,7] and music has always been associated with emotionality [9,26].

Being emotions the main composition medium, the involvement of the performer changes. Therefore, the tradi-

tional paradigm based on a note-to-note control is replaced by compositional decisions based on the emotions the user intends to elicit. This forces the system to include an algorithmic module, which can convert user input into musical language and generate music consequently.

In this paper we introduce Robin, an algorithmic composer designed to make the experience of musical creativity accessible to even untrained people. The main contribution introduced by Robin is the possibility of interacting with music in real time. Users can direct the composition in real time, conveying emotions that are translated into matching music in classical piano style. The potential lack of musical training of the users requires that the generated music should be understandable by everybody. In this connection, tonal music has the potential to reach a wider audience as it is the most common music in Western culture across different age groups and it is gradually spreading to other cultures.

Performing art provides the most important application field for the presented system. In fact, Robin can be used as a basis for interactive installations, where users can direct the music interacting with each other through their own body movements. Basing on this premise, we designed The Music Room, an installation where user couples can experience music creativity by moving throughout an area [5]. Robin also opens a number of possible practical applications in the most diverse fields. For example, movie directors and computer game developers could realize their own soundtracks instead of hiring professional musicians or licensing existing tracks. General technology users may adopt such a system to personalize their personal devices and online services, composing unique ringtones for mobile phones, creating a musical background for personal spaces on social networks (the musical equivalent to the so-called “status” which verbally describes somebody’s moods and feelings), or for shared albums in image hosting websites. From a social perspective, a system that enables non-musicians to translate their own feelings and emotions into music might prove useful for therapeutic purposes.

The paper is organized as follows: in section 2 the related works are reviews; in section 3 Robin’s architecture is described; in section 4 The Music Room is presented; in sections 5 and 6, finally, future developments are pre-figured and some general conclusions are drawn.

2. RELATED WORKS

According to Todd and Werner, research on algorithmic music composition has based its own evolution on three approaches: evolutionary, learning-based and rule-based [10]. Evolutionary algorithms are particularly suitable to ensure an unpredictable outcome over the generative process [3]; the generated music, though, can result complex and unnatural. Learning-based algorithms compute music by training the system with pre-existing musical excerpts [12]. While the result is more natural, it strongly relies on the training set. The rule-based approach to a greater extent depends on human intervention, as compositional rules are manually coded [13]. Thus, a deep knowledge on music theory is required of algorithm designers, and the diversity and quality of musical outcomes depends on the amount of taught rules [14]. Recently, several algorithmic composition systems exploited the relation between music and emotion in the composition process [13,15,16]. In 2009, Hoeberechts and Shantz presented AMEE, a patented algorithmic composer that put the emphasis on automatic generation of soundtracks for video games [15]. In this system, the composition can be influenced in real time by altering the desired mood.

As regards the mapping between music and perceived emotions, research on the psychology of music suggests that the interpretation of emotions in music depends on acoustic cues embedded in composition and performance behaviours, whose combination stirs different emotional responses in the listener [8,9]. Researchers usually adopt a dimensional or a categorical approach to measure and classify emotions. In the categorical approach, emotions are discretized into a number of classes that correspond to the basic emotions. Several studies aimed at defining a set of musical variables, such as tempo, sound level, timbre, vibrato and consonance, that seemed typical of each of the basic emotions elicited by music such as anger, happiness, fear and solemnity [6,11]. The restricted number of categories, however, limits the fullness of emotional states evoked by music [17]. To overcome this limitation, most of the studies describe and measure emotions with a dimensional approach that allows combinations and gradients of emotions [9,13,16,18]. These studies are usually based on Russell's Circumplex theory [19], according to which emotions can be described as a continuum along two dimensions: valence, which refers to the positive vs. negative value of affective states, and arousal, which refers to the rest vs. activation difference.

2.1 Mapping music into valence and arousal

A general consensus suggests that mode and rhythm determine valence, while tempo and dynamics are determine arousal [9]. Other structural parameters that contribute to the elicitation of emotions are volume, melody direction, dissonance and expectation fulfillment. Table 1 shows how the combination of these elements determines the desired emotional expression by means of valence and arousal.

		Valence	Arousal
Mode	Major	Positive	
	Minor	Negative	
Tempo	Fast	Positive (less influential)	High
	Slow	Negative (less influential)	Low
Volume		Decrease in case of very low or very high volumes	Proportional to volume
Melody Direction	Rising	Positive	
	Falling	Negative	
Dissonance		Negative	
Note Density	High		High
	Low		Low
Expect. Fulfillment		Positive	

Table 1. Mapping between musical structures and the emotional dimensions of valence and arousal

Mode. Mode is the compositional factor which mostly influences valence. While minor mode elicits negative valence, major mode elicits positive valence. Mode does not directly impact on arousal [8, 18].

Tempo. Tempo influences the factor of arousal: in particular, fast tempo elicits high arousal, while slow tempo elicits low arousal [8]. Furthermore, to some extent, high tempo elicits positive valence, while slow tempo elicits negative valence [20]. A recent study showed that the influence of tempo on the dimension of valence dimension is to be particularly observed in non-musicians, as they attribute a greater importance to tempo than to mode when evaluating valence [18].

Volume. Volume is directly proportional to the arousal elicited in the listener. In case of very high and very low volume, however, valence is negatively influenced because the listening experience becomes unpleasant [8].

Melody direction. The direction of the melody in a sentence can influence the perceived valence. To some extent, rising melodies express positive emotions, while falling melodies express negative emotions [8].

Dissonance. Traditionally, dissonance can elicit negative valence, especially if the listener is a non-musician [21].

Note density. The density of notes impacts on the arousal dimension [8], which can be altered by the increased level of energy in the composition resulting from a dense melody.

Fulfillment of expectations. In his pioneering book, *Emotion and Meaning in Music*, Leonard Meyer explained how the fulfillment of expectations can elicit positive emotions while listening to a piece of music [22].

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

As Robin is intended to be used in interactive contexts available to everybody, two requirements must be met: i) the generated music needs to be accessible even to non-musicians; ii) the composition has to be influenced in real time. These requirements led to the adoption of a rule-based approach, as it guarantees an accurate control of the compositional process. The algorithm is taught a series of basic compositional rules of tonal music, which are used to create original compositions in Western piano music style. The choice of tonal music is consistent with the ultimate purpose of our research which is targeted at an untrained audience, that usually do not understand experimental, complex or atonal compositions [23]. To ensure consistency with user interaction, the system continuously listens to input changes, adapting the musical outcome accordingly.

Unlike AMEE [15], which puts the emphasis on soundtracks for computer games, Robin does not allow the definition of high-level musical structures, such as verses and sections. This choice was dictated by the fact that the evolution of user interaction with the system cannot be predicted. AMEE tackles this issue by introducing forced abortion in the process of music generation. By contrast, we decided to avoid dramatic interruptions, as to guarantee a musical coherence and a natural evolution of the composition itself. The only high-level structural elements composed by Robin are theme repetitions, which simulate choruses and verses, that are typically present in most of contemporary genres, and cadences that define phrases. Robin is composed of three modules (Figure 1) that independently control different parts of the composition.

Figure 1. The architecture of Robin.

The Harmony Generation Module (HGM) determines the chord progression basing on a probabilistic approach. The generated chords are then fed to the Accompaniment Generation Module (AGM), that composes the *left hand* melody, and to the Melody Generation Module (MGM), that composes the *right hand* accompaniment. The MGM computes the melody notes by combining the rhythmic pattern chosen by the Rhythm Generation Module (RGM) with the pitches chosen by the Pitch Selection Module (PSM).

3.1 Harmony Generation Module

Traditionally, harmony is examined on the basis of chord progressions and cadences. Several algorithms for music compositions based on Generative Grammar implement chord progressions as stochastic processes [14,23]. The transition probabilities between successive chords are defined as Markov processes [23]. Chords transition data can be extracted analyzing existing music, surveying music theory or following personal aesthetic tastes and experiences [24].

In Robin, chords correlation does not depend on previous states of the system. A first-order Markov process determines the harmonic progression as a continuous stream of chords that is sometimes forced to go to a cadence or to modulate. The algorithm controls chord progression, starting from a random key and then iteratively processing a Markov matrix to compute the successive chords (Table 2). The 10x10 matrix contains the transition probabilities among the degrees of the scale. The entries are the seven degrees of the scale as triads in root position and three degrees (II, IV, V) set in the VII chord. The transition probabilities are based on the study of Harmony of Walter Piston [25] and from tonal music literature (mostly from Bach chorales).

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	IV7	V7	II7
I	0	0.05	0.05	0.30	0.20	0.05	0.1	0.05	0.15	0.05
II	0.04	0	0.04	0.04	0.45	0.08	0	0	0.35	0
III	0	0.07	0	0.21	0.07	0.65	0	0	0	0
IV	0.15	0.10	0.05	0	0.35	0.05	0	0	0.30	0
V	0.64	0.05	0.05	0.13	0	0.13	0	0	0	0
VI	0	0.40	0.10	0.10	0	0	0	0	0	0.40
VII	0.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
IV7	0	0.30	0	0	0.30	0.30	0	0	0.10	0
V7	0.9	0	0	0.05	0	0.05	0	0	0	0
II7	0	0	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0.5	0

Table 2. Transition probability matrix among the degrees of the scale.

At each new bar the system analyzes the transition matrix and checks the row corresponding to the degree of the bar playing at that moment. At this point, the degree of the successive bar is computed: the higher the transition value, the higher the probability to be selected. The harmonic rhythm is one bar long and each bar measures $\frac{4}{4}$. In order to divide the composition into phrases, every eight bars the system forces the harmonic progression to a ca-

dence (a conclusion of a phrase or a period) to a perfect or plagal mode. In order to generate compositions with more variations, Robin can switch between different keys and perform V and IV modulations.

3.2 Accompaniment Generation Module

The music generated by Robin consists of two voices: melody and accompaniment. At each new bar, the Accompaniment Generation Module (AGM) selects the new accompaniment. Four sets of clichés (accompaniment typologies) are available. The sets differ in the density of the notes in the arpeggio.

3.3 Melody Generation Module

Melody is computed by separately dealing with rhythm and pitch, thus maintaining coherence in the composition. At each new bar, the Rhythm Generation Module (RGM) selects a rhythmic pattern, which is consistent with the internal state of the system. The rhythmic pattern is then filled with pitches chosen by the Pitch Selection Module (PSM).

3.3.1 Rhythm Generation Module

The RGM is responsible for selecting the rhythmic patterns. A total of 38 possible rhythmic patterns are clustered into 3 sets, depending on the role of the bar in the phrase. The first set includes the rhythmic patterns suitable for the initial bars and for every bar in the phrase except the final one. The second set is responsible for lending an original character to each composition. The rhythmic patterns for all the bars except for the initial and the final ones belong to this set, that we divided into the following four subsets:

- 2a. Patterns with a predominance of quarter notes.
- 2b. Patterns with a number of 8th and 16th notes.
- 2c. Patterns with triplets.
- 2d. Patterns with syncopated rhythms.

The patterns belonging to the second category are selected with a stochastic approach. The computation of harmonic progression was defined as a stochastic process. Similarly, a probability-based squared matrix for rhythmic patterns is defined (Table 3). The rows and the columns represent the five rhythmic pattern subsets suitable for the internal bars (1, 2a, 2b, 2c, 2d), while the individual items of the matrix represent the transition probabilities. Unlike the harmonic progression, the conditional probability distribution of future rhythmic patterns depends on the sequence of events that preceded it. This choice aims at increasing the coherence in the composition, thus influencing the choice of rhythmic patterns on previous decisions. As a consequence, the rhythm probability matrix is dynamically updated at each step. For instance, when the algorithm repeatedly chooses patterns from the 2c subset, the probability of staying in the same subset increases at the expense of the other three subsets.

	1	2a	2b	2c	2d
1	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
2a	0.10	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.20
2b	0.05	0.1	0.35	0.20	0.30
2c	0.05	0.2	0.2	0.35	0.2
2d	0.05	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.35

Table 3. Transition probability matrix for rhythmic patterns of internal bars. At each step, the matrix dynamically updates in relation to the history of the system.

The third set is composed of the rhythmic patterns used in the last bars of each phrase. This set is also divided into two subsets: the algorithm selects patterns from the 3a or 3b subset if most of the bars of the phrase were taken respectively from 2a, 2b or from 2c, 2d:

- 3a. Patterns of the cadences to 2a and 2b.
- 3b. Patterns of the cadences to 2c and 2d

3.3.2 Pitch Selection Module

The Pitch Selection Module (PSM) receives the rhythmic pattern and the current chord from RGM and HGM (Figure 2a). The selection of the notes of the melody occurs in two steps. In the first step (Figure 2b), all the significant notes in the bar are filled with notes of the chord. The notes regarded as significant are those whose duration is eighth or longer or that are in a relevant position in the bar (e.g. first and last place). At the second step (Figure 2c), the algorithm fills the remaining spaces with notes of the scale. Starting from the leftmost note, when the algorithm bumps into an empty space, it checks the note on the left and it steps one pitch up or one pitch down, depending on the value of the melody direction.

Figure 2. The selection of pitches for the melody. a) The PSM receives the rhythmic pattern and the chord. b) The relevant notes of the melody are filled with notes of the chord. c) The remaining spaces are filled with notes of the scale to form a descending or ascending melody.

3.4 User Intervention: emotional change

The theoretical foundations for the mapping between music and emotion adopted in our work were reviewed in 2.1. The concepts expressed in Table 1 are operationalized in Robin as follows:

Mode. The change between modes is supported by Robin in the HGM that populates the matrix with notes in the selected mode.

Tempo. Tempo is managed by Robin as a continuous variable measured in BPM.

Volume. Volume is a continuous variable that determines the intensity (velocity) of the musical outcome.

Melody direction. The direction of the melody is determined by the PSM as described in 3.3.2.

Dissonance. Dissonance is achieved by inserting a number of out-of-scale notes in both melody and harmony.

Note density. Note density is manipulated by means of clichés and rhythmic patterns.

Fulfillment expectations. We operationalized this concept by presenting a theme several times. Repeated themes, indeed, elicit positive valence as they builds memories and expectations in the listeners.

4. ROBIN IN THE CONTEXT OF PERFORMING ART: THE MUSIC ROOM

The Music Room is an interactive installation for collaborative music composition that represents the first interface to Robin [5]. Two people direct the composition of original piano music by moving throughout a room. Information about the emotionality of music is inferred from proxemics cues by following the analogy with love: high proximity is mapped into positive emotions and low proximity into negative emotions; high speed into intense emotions and low speed into mild emotions. The first versions of The Music Room were exhibited at the EU Researchers' Night, (Trento, Italy, September 28th 2012) and at the ICT Days (Trento, Italy, March 23th 2013¹). The 5x5m room that hosted the installation was deliberately empty and minimally decorated, as to draw the attention of people to the musical cue.

The architecture consists of a Position Tracking Module and Robin. The acquisition of proxemic cues is performed through a camera in a bird eye position, fixed on the ceiling in the center of the room. Moving people are detected and followed through a visual tracking algorithm; their position is updated over time, processed and then sent to Robin. The cues of interest are the relative distance and average speed, computed according to the trajectory of each user over time. The information coming from the proxemic cues computed by the tracking

system conveys the intended emotionality. By matching the values of speed and proximity to emotions, Robin adapts the musical flow, as has been previously described. The system is developed in SuperCollider, a programming language for audio synthesis and algorithmic composition. The software outputs a MIDI score that is transformed by Logic Pro, a Digital Audio Workstation, into piano music.

After each session, couples were given a link to a webpage where they could fill an evaluation questionnaire and download the song that Robin composed during their experience. The results of the questionnaire showed that most of the visitors (76%) greatly appreciated the installation and in particular the quality of the music (79%). Criticism was mostly aimed at the latency of the system response to user movements and at the lack of musical genres. Nevertheless, almost the 90% of the interviewees had an overall enjoyable experience.

5. FUTURE WORKS

Even though this system has already met with considerable appreciation, some limitations do exert an influence on the current version of the algorithm. In particular, the originality and the diversity of the compositions are affected by the absence of a bass line and by the lack of available genres. In order to improve the quality and diversity of the generated music, a number of new features are being currently developed. Among them, we are envisioning the possibility of extending the MGM to support multiple voices and the harmonic progression matrix to support chords in non-root position.

Furthermore, we are currently developing more musical genres and instruments, as to enable users to choose their favorite musical style before trying the installation. As regards the mapping of music with emotions, we are planning to increase the number of musical parameters that provoke a change in the elicited emotions. Among these parameters, we plan to include tensions and level of orchestration to map arousal, and timbre, number of harmonics and melodic range to map valence.

The latency between the user input and the musical output represents another limitation of the system. Even though the musical system is specifically designed to synchronize the user input with the generated music, we purposely decided to avoid sudden changes in music. This choice was mainly dictated by aesthetic reasons, requiring the phraseological structure of music to be preserved even in case of rapid changes in the emotional input. For this purpose, the successive musical phrase is computed at the last beat of the playing bar, currently fixed at $\frac{4}{4}$. This results in an approximately 4-second delay, in the worst-case scenario, occurring with a 60 BPM tempo and the bar at the first beat. Two solutions allow the new version of the algorithm to reduce this latency, while preserving musical coherence.

1. At every quarter, a new input from the user is checked. If it ranks above or below a specific threshold, a new bar starts straightaway.

¹ Some excerpts of the generated music can be found at <http://goo.gl/Ulhgz>

2. The tempo range is changed from 60-140 to 90-150 BPM. As a consequence, each beat lasts 0.75 seconds, while 90 BPM is still slow enough to be perceived as *andante*.

By implementing these solutions, the latency time drops to 0.75 seconds in the worst-case scenario: this figure can be regarded as sufficiently low even for interactive situations.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The importance of emotion-driven real-time algorithmic composition systems was already discussed by relevant studies [15,16]. In this connection, Robin represents a new approach in the context of interactive scenarios. The appreciation of the attendees of the two editions of the Music Rooms clearly witnesses to the quality of the music. Due to this success, a number of other installations based on Robin are currently being developed for educational, entertainment and therapeutic purposes.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Bischoff, J., Gold, R. and Horton, J. Music for an interactive Network of Microcomputers. *Computer Music Journal*, 2(3), (1978), pp. 24-29.
- [2] Jordà, S., Geiger, G., Alonso, M., and Kaltenbrunner, M. The ReacTable: Exploring the synergy between live music performance and tabletop tangible interfaces. *Proc. TEI 2007*, (2007).
- [3] Miranda, E.R., & Biles, J.A. *Evolutionary Computer Music*. Springer, (2007).
- [4] Cope, D. *Computer Models of Musical Creativity*. The MIT Press, (2005).
- [5] Morreale, F., Masu, R., De Angeli, A., Rota, P. The Music Room. *CHI '13 Extended Abstracts*. (2013).
- [6] Gabrielsson, A, Juslin, P. N. Emotional Expression In Music Performance: Between the Performer's Intention and the Listener's Experience. *Psychology of Music*. (1996). 24(1), 68-91.
- [7] Balkwill, L. L., Thompson, W. F., & Matsunaga, R. I. E. Recognition of emotion in Japanese, Western, and Hindustani music by Japanese listeners. *Japanese Psychological Research*, 46(4), (2004), pp. 337-349.
- [8] Gabrielsson A., Lindröm, E. The role of structure in the musical expression of emotions. In: P. N. Juslin, & J.A. Sloboda (Eds.), *Handbook of music and emotion: Theory, research, applications*, New York: Oxford University Press, (2010), pp. 367-400.
- [9] Juslin P.N., Sloboda J.A. *Handbook of music and emotion: theory, research, applications*. Oxford University Press, (2010).
- [10] Todd, P. M., & Werner, G. M. *Frankensteinian methods for evolutionary music composition*. Musical networks: Parallel distributed perception and performance, (1999) pp. 313-339.
- [11] Juslin, P., Laukka, P. (2004). Expression, Perception, and Induction of Musical Emotions: A Review and a Questionnaire Study of Everyday Listening. *Journal of New Music Research*, 33(3), 217-238.
- [12] Simon, I., Morris, D., & Basu, S. MySong: automatic accompaniment generation for vocal melodies. *Proc. of the twenty-sixth annual CHI'08*. ACM, (2008), pp. 725-734.
- [13] Wallis, I., Ingalls, T., Campana, E., Goodman, J.: A Rule-Based Generative Music System Controlled By Desired Valence and Arousal. *Proc. SMC 2011*, (2011).
- [14] Steedman, M. A Generative grammar for jazz chord sequences. *Music Perception Vol. 2*, No. 1, (1984).
- [15] Hoeberechts, M., & Shantz, J. (n.d.). Real-Time Emotional Adaptation in Automated Composition. *Proceedings of Audio Mostly, 2009* (pp. 1-8).
- [16] Livingstone, S., Mühlberger, R., Brown, A., & Loch, A. Controlling musical emotionality: an affective computational architecture for influencing musical emotions. *Digital Creativity*, 18(1), (2007). 43-53.
- [17] Scherer, K. R. Which Emotions Can be Induced by Music? What Are the Underlying Mechanisms? And How Can We Measure Them? *Journal of New Music Research*. (2004). 33(2), 239-251.
- [18] Morreale, F., Masu, R., De Angeli, A., Fava, P. The effect of expertise in evaluating emotions in music. *Proc. of the 3rd International Conference on Music & Emotion*. (2013).
- [19] Russell, J. A circumplex model of affect. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, (1980).
- [20] Gagnon, L. Peretz I. Mode and tempo relative contributions to "happy-sad" judgments in equitone melodies. *Cognition and emotions*, 40, (2003), pp. 17-25.
- [21] Fritz T., Jentschke S., Gosselin N., Sammler D., Peretz I., et al. Universal Recognition of Three Basic Emotions in Music. *Current Biology*, (2009), pp. 573-576.
- [22] L. B. Meyer, *Emotion and meaning in music*. University of Chicago Press, (1956).
- [23] Nierhaus, G. *Algorithmic Composition: Paradigms of Automated Music Generation*. Springer, (2009).
- [24] Chai W. Vercoe B., Folk music Classification using Hidden Markov Models (2001), *Proc. of ICAI 01*, (2011).
- [25] Piston W. DeVoto M, *Harmony*. Norton, (1941).
- [26] Cooke D. *The language of music*: London: Oxford University Press, (1959).